

Chloral Derivatives of Salicylic Acid.

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During the course of their work on chlorides (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 545) the present authors tried to prepare the salicylic acid chloralide. The condensation was tried under varying conditions: (a) Wallach's method (*Annalen*, 1878, 193, 1), was repeated to no advantage; (b) the condensation was repeated in presence of different condensing agents, *viz.*, glacial acetic acid, concentrated hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid; acetic acid and hydrochloric acid did not effect the condensation, while sulphuric acid gave a product from which no crystalline substance could be separated (*cf.* Chattaway and Calvet, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1090).

The present authors, thinking that this complexity was due to the activity of OH-group in the salicylic acid, decided to study the condensation with the methyl ether of salicylic acid. After this work on methyl ether derivatives had proceeded, our attention was drawn to a paper by Hurry and Meldrum (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 535) on some derivatives of *o*-methoxybenzoic acid along similar lines. This rendered much of our work superfluous and although we confirm their results in general, the results obtained so far are interesting enough for publication.

It is found that in addition to the product (I, R=CHOH·CCl₃) there is present in the sulphuric acid filtrate a sulphonic acid, which is easily converted into it on boiling. This accounts for the low

(I)

yield of (I, R=CHOH·CCl₃) obtained by Hurry and Meldrum (*loc. cit.*). Generally the products obtained by Hurry and Meldrum are not well purified; this can be seen from the following table.

Substance.	Hurry and Meldrum (m.p.).	Shah and Alimchandani (m.p.).
Condensation product (I, R = CHOH·CCl ₃)	216°	224°
Reduction product (I, R = CH ₂ CHCl ₂)	127°	134-35°
Tetrachloro product (I, R = CHCl·CCl ₃)	132°	138°

The action of bromine and of dry HCl as described by Yelburgi and Wheeler (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 217) was tried on the reduction product (I, R = CH₂·CHCl₂) with no effect. This proves that it has the saturated formula containing the group CH₂CHCl₂. The reduction product (I, R = CH₂CHCl₂) on treatment with concentrated H₂SO₄ gave 4-methoxy-5-carboxyphenylacetic acid (I, R = CH₂·COOH). The condensation product (I, R = CHOH·CCl₃) was treated with sulphuric acid. A yellow mass was obtained from which two products were separated: (a) colourless crystals, m.p. 138°, found to be identical with Hurry and Meldrum's 5-carboxy-4-methoxy-1- α - $\beta\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethylbenzene (I, R = CHCl·CCl₃) and (b) a substance in a very small quantity, m.p. 177°, which could not be investigated further.

The above condensation of chloral, however, excludes the possibility of the chloralide formation. The reactivity of the free acid may perhaps be moderated by the introduction of suitable substituents in the nucleus. With this end in view, we studied the condensation with 3-nitro- and 5-nitrosalicylic acids and their methyl ethers (*Current Science*, 1935, **3**, 354). We then tried to condense chloral with 3-amino-, 5-amino-, 5-sulpho-, and 5-bromosalicylic acids by different methods. In all these cases, the condensation could not be effected. Details of these unsuccessful attempts to condense chloral with the substituted salicylic acids are omitted from the experimental part.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Salicylic acid has been methylated according to the method of Meldrum and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 1987). The methoxy acid after recrystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether melts at 106° (Meldrum and Shah, *in.p.* 100-5°).

4-Methoxy-5-carboxy-1- α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzene (I, R = CHOH·CCl₃).—Finely powdered methoxysalicylic acid (10 g.), chloral hydrate (12 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) were mixed and the clear solution after keeping for 5 days was poured into ice, when a pasty mass separated which solidified on washing with water. It crystallised from boiling glacial acetic acid in small needles;

recrystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 224° . (Found : Cl, 35'44. Calc. for $C_{10}H_5O_4Cl_3$: Cl, 35'54 per cent).

The sulphuric acid filtrate was evaporated in an air-oven when white crystals began to separate, which were found to be identical with the condensation product, total yield 9 g.

Reduction product (I, $R=CH_2\cdot CHCl_2$).—To the hot solution of the above substance (5 g.) in acetic acid (25 c.c.), zinc dust (4 g.) was gradually added in small amount and the mixture was filtered from unchanged zinc and the filtrate diluted with water, when a white light substance came down. It was first crystallised from acetic acid and then from benzene, m.p. $134-35^{\circ}$, yield almost theoretical. (Found : C, 48'22; H, 3'63; Cl, 28'35. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{10}O_3Cl_2$: C, 48'2; H, 4'01; Cl, 28'5 per cent).

4-Methoxy-5-carboxyphenylacetic Acid (I, $R=CH_2\cdot COOH$).—The reduction product (5 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) on a water-bath when HCl gas was evolved. After the reaction was over, the mixture was poured into ice-cold water when the crystals slowly separated. It crystallised from water with 1 H_2O , m.p. $141-42^{\circ}$. (Found : H_2O , 7'7; Equiv., 114'3. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$, 1 H_2O requires H_2O , 7'89 per cent. Equiv., 114). It crystallised from a mixture of acetone and benzene as clusters of long silky needles, m.p. 153° . (Found : Equiv., 105'5. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires Equiv., 105).

Action of Sulphuric acid on the substance (I, $R=CHOH\cdot CCl_3$).—The substance (1 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) and heated on a water-bath for about an hour. Effervescence of HCl gas began at about 75° and the colour of the solution turned brown. After the reaction was over, the mixture was cooled and poured into cold water when a yellow pasty mass separated which slowly solidified on washing with water. On crystallising from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether and then from ethyl acetate, two types of crystals were observed : (i) colourless prismatic, m.p. 135° ; (ii) deep yellow, m.p. 170° . The prismatic crystals on further recrystallisation from acetic acid melted at 138° . This was found to be identical with Hurry and Meldrum's tetrachloro derivative (I, $CHCl\cdot CCl_3$). From deep yellow material, a very small quantity of a coloured product m.p. 177° , was obtained which could not be further investigated.

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